

PENGEMBANGAN MULTIMEDIA INTERAKTIF “SCRIBER” UNTUK PESERTA DIDIK SEKOLAH MENENGAH PERTAMA

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Submitted
2021-09-13

Accepted
2021-11-23

Published
2021-12-13

Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian adalah mengembangkan multimedia interaktif “SCRIBER” (*Social Studies Learning-Based Articulate Storyline*) tentang Potensi Sumber Daya Alam dan Kemaritiman Indonesia yang valid dan efektif untuk digunakan dalam pembelajaran. Penelitian menggunakan metode penelitian dan pengembangan (R&D) dengan model pengembangan penilaian dan analisis, desain, pengembangan, implementasi, dan evaluasi. Subjek penelitian yaitu 2 dosen dan 32 peserta didik. Validasi instrumen menggunakan angket validasi dan angket respons peserta didik yang menunjukkan produk yang dikembangkan layak. Teknik analisis data menggunakan deskriptif kualitatif dan kuantitatif dengan perhitungan skor menggunakan skala Likert dan Guttman. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa ahli media menyatakan bahwa produk yang dikembangkan termasuk pada kriteria sangat layak, penilaian materi termasuk pada kriteria sangat layak, respons peserta didik terhadap produk yang dikembangkan termasuk pada kriteria sangat baik, dan efektif digunakan dalam proses pembelajaran..

Kata Kunci: Articulate Storyline; multimedia interaktif; SCRIBER.

Abstract

The research aimed to develop interactive multimedia “SCRIBER” (Social Studies Learning-Based Articulate Storyline) about the Potential of Indonesian Maritime and Natural Resources valid and effective for use in learning. The research used the research and development (R&D) method with the analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation development model. The research subjects were 2 lecturers and 32 students. The validation of the research results was carried out by expert validators and students. The data analysis technique used descriptive qualitative and quantitative with the calculation of scores using the Likert and the Guttman scale. The results showed that the media experts stated that the developed product was included in the very feasible criteria, the material assessment included the very feasible criteria, the student's responses to the developed product included the very good criteria and the effectiveness obtained from the posttest results was higher than the pretest results.

Keywords: Articulate Storyline; interactive multimedia; SCRIBER.